

Some characteristics of jute caddies with reference to briquetting and gasification

L. K. Nayak*, A. K. Roy and S. Das

National Institute of Research on Jute & Allied Fibre Technology, 12, Regent Park, Kolkata-700 040, India

E-mail : laxmikanta8495@rediffmail.com Fax : 91-33-24712583

Manuscript received 01 June 2010, revised 27 July 2010, accepted 28 July 2010

Abstract : Caddies, the unspinnable short jute fibre is the waste produced at different unit operations in the jute mill, which cannot be processed further. It constitutes about 1.5–3.0% of the raw fibre processed in the jute mill. This industrial waste can be utilized as potential biomass for gasification after briquetting. An attempt has been made to characterize this mill waste through proximate and thermal analysis. Binder less briquettes of jute caddies in combination with other agro-residues like sawdust and rice husk have been produced in a 125 kg/h capacity briquetting machine. The calorific value of jute caddies as such is 3920 kcal/kg. However, after mixing with saw dust and rice husk in the proportion of (40 : 60), the calorific value increases upto 4148 kcal/kg. These briquettes have been used successfully in a downdraft gasifier for generation of producer gas.

Keywords : Caddies, briquetting, gasification, energy.

Introduction

The caddies in combination with other mill waste creates serious problem in storage due to its low density values. It also adds to the environmental pollution, when enters into the atmospheric air as dust particles. Traditionally the jute industry used this waste along with coal as fuel for the boiler to generate steam which was required to run the sizing and calendaring machines. Use of caddies as fuel is problematic, mainly because of its poor fuel value and thermal efficiency and low bulk density. Briquetting is a technology for densification of biomass for easy handling, transport, storage and uniform burning (when used for energy). Briquettes have high specific density, about 1100–1200 kg/m³ and bulk density about 600–800 kg/m³ as compared to loose biomass which have bulk density in the range of 80–200 kg/m³. Gasification technology has been considered as one of the effective and economic methods for conversion of biomass to energy.

Results and discussion

Biomass is a natural product of solar energy, and therefore, a renewable source of carbon and hydrogen which are the basic constituents of energy and chemical prod-

ucts. The proximate analysis of jute caddies shows that, it contains volatile matter of 78.71%, fixed carbon of 12.19% and ash content of 9.10%. The results indicate that the ash content of caddies is higher than that of jute stick (1–2%) due to the presence of high amount of dust particles, soil etc. Based on the ash content, caddies can be classified as medium ash (5–10%) material and be useful as a potential raw material for energy conversion processes. The high ash content containing alkali metal oxides like Na, K and Ca tends to lower the fusion temperature of ash. This low ash sintering temperatures tend to form clinkers during combustion/gasification and is detrimental to the smooth operation of these high temperature working appliances. It is therefore imperative to know both ash deformation and ash fusion temperature in order to find the suitability for energy conversion and design and operate the energy conversion devices. The ash deformation and ash fusion temperature of jute caddies was found to be 850 °C and 950 °C respectively. The value shows that caddies has a tendency for clinker formation at a slightly low temperature than in comparison to other agro-residues with ash deformation and fusion temperature above 1000 °C.

For the process parameters, the optimum moisture

content of jute caddies for grinding in hammer mill and feeding into briquetting plant (in mixing with saw dust and rice husk) was found to be 10–15% (w.b). For production of briquettes of stable configuration, a ratio of 40 : 60 for both the mixture (caddies and rice husk, 40 : 60) and (caddies and saw dust, 40 : 60) was found optimum for briquetting machine. The briquettes thus produced were used as fuel in the gasifier unit (10 kg/h capacity) and was found suitable in generating the producer gas. The producer gas is having composition (v/v) viz. $\text{CO}_2 = 8\text{--}10\%$, $\text{O}_2 \leq 1\%$, $\text{CO} = 24\text{--}26\%$, $\text{CH}_4 = 1.5\text{--}2\%$, $\text{H}_2 = 10\text{--}12\%$ and $\text{N}_2 = 54\text{--}56\%$ with gross calorific value of 1200–1350 kcal/m³. The amount of producer gas produced from jute caddies briquettes depends on the efficiency of gasifier. Considering the efficiency of the gasifier unit (10 kg/h capacity) as 70%, the average production of producer gas is 2.28 m³/kg of briquettes.

Experimental

Proximate analysis :

The analysis involves determination of moisture content, volatile matter, fixed carbon and ash. Initially 5 g of caddies sample was taken and was heated in the absence of oxygen at 110 °C. The weight loss was recorded as 0.455 g, which was the moisture content calculated as 9.10%.

After evaluation of moisture content, the remaining mass i.e. 4.545 g (5.00–0.455) was taken as 100% and volatile matter, fixed carbon and ash content was calculated at each step of heating. As the temperature increased further to about 250–300 °C, the material decomposed and gases and liquids in the form of volatiles get released. The process completed at 700 °C. During heating in the range of 250–700 °C the weight loss recorded was 3.577 g which was 78.71% of 4.545 g and termed as volatile matter. At this stage the solid residue left back was the mixture of carbon as coke and ash contents of the sample. The temperature was increased further to 900 °C and weight loss was recorded as 0.554 g which was 12.19% of 4.545 g and termed as carbon content. The amount left out i.e. 0.414 g (4.545–3.577–0.554) which was 9.10% of 4.545 was termed as ash content of the sample.

Ash deformation and fusion temperatures :

Jute caddies is put in muffle furnace at 750 °C till constant weight is obtained. Residual part (Ash) is finely ground and a solution (10% dextrin, 0.1% salicylic acid and 89.9% H₂O) is added to bring the ash to plastic stage.

The paste is moulded to conical shape. The cone are removed from moulds and allowed to dry. Dried cones are kept on a refractory base after which these are kept in high temperature muffle furnace and heated to 800 °C. After each 15 min the temperature is raised with an increment of 50 °C. During each interval the shape of cone is observed. The range of temperature at which the bending or initial rounding off of the apex of the cone is observed is known as ash deformation temperature. By increasing the temperature further, the cone fuse to a hemispherical lump, this temperature range is known as ash fusion temperature.

Briquetting of jute caddies :

Fig. 1 shows the caddies received from the jute mill. It contains lots of foreign particles, dust particles, jute stick chips and other unwanted material that accumulated during the course of jute fibre processing. Before subjecting the caddies into the hammer mill, it was cleaned manually for smooth functioning of the size reduction process.

Fig. 1. Caddies received from jute mill

Due to the fibrous nature of caddies, it is not easily flowable in the briquetting plant. Hence, it was mixed with rice husk and saw dust in the proportion of 40 : 60 for increasing its flow ability and calorific values (Fig. 2). The calorific values of briquettes were increased from 3920–4148 kcal/kg due to the mixing of saw dust

Fig. 2. Caddies mixed with saw dust and rice husk

Note

and rice husk. Saw dust and rice husk has the calorific values of 3728 kcal/kg and 3826 kcal/kg respectively.

Fig. 3 shows the briquettes prepared from mixture of jute caddies with saw dust and jute caddies with rice husk.

Fig. 3. Briquettes prepared from jute caddies

It's evident from Fig. 3 that briquettes so produced are stable in configuration for easy feeding into the gasifier plant for production of producer gas.

Acknowledgement

Authors are grateful to Director, NIRJAFT for his constant encouragement.

References

- 1 P K Ganguly, S K Bhaduri and A Dey, *Journal of Scientific and Industrial Research* 2004, **63**, 417
- 2 P D Grover, "Characterization of Biomass for Energy Generation", Proceedings of National Seminar on "Biomass Management for Energy Purposes – Issues and Strategies" held at Anand, Gujarat during 11-12 December, 2004
- 3 B S Pathak, A K Jain and A Singh *Agricultural Wastes* 1986, **16**, 27
- 4 M Shyam, *Agricultural Engineering Today*, 1987, **11**, 24
- 5 P K Srivastava and S S Tomar, *Agricultural Engineering Today*, 1993, **17**, 1
- 6 G C Wakchaure and P K Sharma, *Journal of Agricultural Engineering*, 2007, **44**, 48

